

SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY LAMINATE FOR DESIGN OF SELF-FOLDING RECONFIGURABLE STRUCTURES

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Abstract

In this work, we examine a self-folding material system that consists of an active laminate including two outer layers of thermally-actuated shape memory alloy (SMA) separated by a compliant passive layer. Localized SMA actuation enables control of the local Gaussian curvature anywhere in the sheet, allowing the initially planar laminate sheet to reconfigure into a 3D structure. The laminate extends the “programmable matter” concept since it can be formed and reconfigured in three dimensions without external manipulations. Two designs have been considered for the self-folding laminate sheet: one design proposes pre-strained thin SMA films for the outer layers of the laminate while the other proposes meshes of pre-strained SMA wires for such layers. The folding performances of these two designs are compared via finite element simulations. The results show that the mesh-based design provides tighter folds at any orientation than the film-based design for the same amount of volume-specific applied power. The mesh-based design shows other attractive qualities such as lower laminate density, less difficult SMA pre-straining process, and reduction of negative effects due to heat transfer between the SMA layers. However, the film-based design provides the advantage of a homogeneous and isotropic folding performance unlike the mesh-based design, where the folding performance depends on orientation and location of the heating zone.

1 Introduction

Numerous engineering devices and structures have been inspired by the art and theory of origami. Origami-inspired structures may offer advantages such as the capability of the structures to be folded

into compact forms for storage (e.g., solar arrays, space structures, and air bags), reduced manufacturing complexity, and the potential for structures to be reconfigurable. Existing applications of origami engineering include: architectural structures [1], several space structures [2], self-deployable stents [3], foldcore-based composites for enhanced mechanical properties and impact resistance behavior [4, 5], and origami-based manufacturing of three-dimensional microstructures and nanostructures [6].

Material systems with self-folding capabilities are of special interest in origami engineering. A self-folding material system can perform folding operations without manipulations from external forces. Self-folding is necessary in circumstances where it is impractical to exert external manipulations to generate the desired folds (e.g., at large scales, or in remote applications such as space or underwater systems). Previous examples of self-folding material systems include the “programmable matter” demonstrations [7], potential biomedical devices [8] and microelectromechanical systems [9] that fold due to surface tension and/or biochemical stimuli, and polymer sheets that generate local folds activated by light absorption [10].

One approach to the design of self-folding material systems is to leverage the multifunctionality of certain materials (e.g., active materials) to generate forces and displacements via non-mechanical applied fields. Active materials can provide considerable motion when stimulated by imposed fields. For instance, shape memory alloys (SMAs) are metallic alloys that undergo solid-to-solid reversible phase transformations induced by temperature and stress fields and during which they can provide uniaxial strains of 5-10% [11].

This work considers a particular kind of active composite incorporating SMAs [12]. Specifically, we consider the localized actuation of a thin laminate sheet composed of layers of active and traditional materials to achieve self-folding behavior. The outer layers of the laminate are composed of active shape memory alloy (SMA) while the inner layer is composed of a compliant passive material. Layers of SMA on both faces of the laminate allow folds in both the positive and negative directions relative to the laminate normal. In the current design, self-generated folds are created by localized SMA actuation, which enables control of the Gaussian curvature anywhere in the laminate, allowing the initially planar laminate to reconfigure into a 3D structure. Moreover, due to the reversible nature of the martensitic phase transformation in SMAs, all folds are reversible, meaning that the system is entirely reprogrammable. Self-construction of useful 3D static and locomotive devices and structures at remote locations from initially compact planar sheets is one of the potential applications for structures composed of this laminate. Schematics of such applications are presented in Fig. 1.

The goal of this work is to analyze and compare the

folding performance of two designs for the proposed self-folding laminate. One design considers the outer layers of the laminate to be composed of pre-strained SMA films [12] while the other considers the outer layers to be composed meshes of woven pre-strained SMA wires [13]. The two considered designs are described in Section 2. Section 3 contains a description of the design parameters that define the self-folding laminate. The analysis methods and tools are described in Section 4. Section 5 presents the results and discussion, and Section 6 contains the conclusions.

2 Design Options for SMA-based Self-Folding Laminates

The general design concept of an SMA-based self-folding laminate consists of three thin layers. The outside layers have been proposed to be thin films of pre-strained thermally-activated SMA material [12] or meshes composed of woven pre-strained SMA wires [13]. The two design options are illustrated in Fig. 2. The outer active layers are separated by a thermally insulating but compliant material such as an elastomer. The function of the SMA outer layers is to provide actuation that generates local bending of the laminate, which creates the folds. The side of the laminate being heated determines the direction of the fold. Unless restricted mechanically, the laminate will return to its initially flat configuration once the SMA cools.

It was shown in a previous work that the SMA film-based laminate design can achieve reprogrammable self-folding behavior [12]. Nevertheless, it was also observed that unintended heat transfer between the two SMA layers could work against the folding operations. Other problem expected with the film-based design option is the difficulty of pre-straining the SMA thin films homogeneously during fabrication.

The mesh design consists of two orthogonal sets of parallel SMA wires. Several options exist for the installation of the SMA meshes relative to the other in terms of relative translation and angle. The *aligned-staggered mesh* design is considered in this work [13]. In this design, the meshes are co-oriented but offset by one half period in the two planar coordinates as shown in Fig. 2. This design is effective in reducing the effects of undesired heat

Fig. 1. Potential applications of the SMA-based self-folding laminate: (a) locomotion by worm-like walking; (b) locomotion by rolling; (c) and (d) examples of self-constructed 3D structures via active folding operations.

transfer between the SMA layers that could work against the folding operation [13]. It should be noted that an SMA material can provide its maximum recoverable uniaxial strain magnitude (denoted H) in a wire form. Such material can also provide bi-direction strain in film form; however, due to the constraints of nearly isochoric response [11], with a maximum balanced in-plane magnitude of $H/2$.

Fig. 2. Schematics of film and mesh design for SMA-based self-folding sheets.

3 Parameterization of the Designs

Schematics of the geometric parameters of the two designs are presented in Fig. 3 [13]. The thickness of the SMA layers, t_w , is considered a fundamental geometric parameter. Two non-dimensional parameters based on t_w are also defined in this study: the heating factor (f_h) and the wire spacing factor (f_s). Those two parameters are given by the following expressions:

$$f_h = \frac{l_h}{t_w} \quad (1)$$

$$f_s = \frac{s}{t_w} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Schematics of film and mesh design for SMA-based self-folding sheets showing geometric parameters.

where l_h is the length of the zone in which power is applied and s is the distance between the centers of two parallel adjacent wires (this parameter only exist for the mesh-based design). A final geometric parameter is the thickness of the elastomer layer, defined as t_{el} .

In addition to the choice of geometric parameters, the power history applied to the SMA must be defined. The total power applied to the wires is defined by the symbol \hat{P}_T . The homogeneous volume-specific heat source applied to the wires (\hat{P}_T) is calculated using Eq. 3.

$$\hat{P}_T = \frac{P_T}{V_h} \quad (3)$$

where V_h is the total volume of the wires located inside the heating zone. The thermal load profile is shown in Fig. 4. The volume-specific heat source increases smoothly from 0% to 100% (full power) during 1 second. Subsequently, 100% power is held constant for the rest of the heating period. Values for the design parameters used in this study were obtained from a previous optimization study [14]. The optimization consisted in determining what values for the design parameters provide the “tightest” fold possible subjected to stress and temperature constraints. The model used for optimization considered a fold generated by heating a region aligned with the meshes containing a single period of SMA wires in a mesh-based self-folding sheet [14]. The values of the design parameters are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Smooth thermal load profile.

Table 1. Values for the geometric and power input parameters [14].

Parameter	Value*
t_w	0.49 mm
f_s	13 (mesh design only)
t_{el}	0.2 mm
\hat{P}_T	0.0883 W/mm ³

*These values were determined for $f_h = 10$.

The output parameter considered in this study is the folding angle (θ). Folding angle θ is the angle between two line segments stretching from the fold apex to the free ends of the sheet. A value of θ equal to 180° corresponds to no fold (flat sheet) while a

value of θ equal to 0° corresponds to full fold. A schematic of the self-folding laminate geometry defined by θ is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Geometry of the folded laminate.

4 Analysis

The analysis described herein follows the framework summarized in detail elsewhere [15], though here we do not utilize the simulation process management tools.

4.1 Material Properties

The elastomer is assumed to be linearly elastic and nearly incompressible. The elastomer material properties are presented in Table 2. The SMA material properties used in this analysis are given in Table 3 and are associated with the thermomechanical constitutive model proposed by Lagoudas and coworkers [16]. Note these properties represent information from a number of scattered and informal sources, and though approximately correct for some materials, will require further investigation prior to more detailed design studies.

Table 2. Elastomer material properties assumed for the analysis of the self-folding sheet.

Property	Value
Density	3000 kg/m ³
<i>(Elastic Properties)</i>	
Elastic modulus (E^{el})	0.1 GPa
Poisson's ratio (ν^{el})	0.45
<i>(Thermal Properties)</i>	
Conductivity	0.15 W/(m K)
Specific heat	141 J/(kg K)

Table 3. SMA material properties assumed for the analysis of the self-folding sheet. Properties are associated with the model of [16].

Property	Value
Density	6450 kg/m ³
<i>(Thermoelastic Properties)</i>	
Elastic modulus of austenite (E^A)	70 GPa
Elastic modulus of martensite (E^M)	30 GPa
Poisson's ratio ($\nu^A = \nu^M$)	0.33
Thermal expansion coefficient (α)	0
<i>(Phase Diagram Properties)</i>	
Martensitic start temperature at zero stress (M_s)	293 K
Martensitic finish temperature at zero stress (M_f)	283 K
Austenitic start temperature at zero stress (A_s)	303 K
Austenitic finish temperature at zero stress (A_f)	313 K
Stress influence coefficients ($C^M = C^A$)	10 MPa/K
<i>(Transformation Strain Properties)</i>	
Uniaxial transformation strain (H)	5.0%
<i>(Smooth Hardening Properties)</i>	
Hardening coefficients ($n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = n_4$)	0.8
<i>(Thermal Properties)</i>	
Conductivity	10 W/(m K)
Specific heat	320 J/(kg K)

4.2 Models

The film-based design will generate folds of equal quality regardless the orientation of the heating zone due to isotropy in the laminate plane. However, the mesh-based design does not have this property. For this reason, a number of cases are considered for the mesh-based design in regard of the orientation of the heating zone with respect to the mesh alignment. The cases are presented in Fig. 6. For the mesh design, an aligned fold (0° angle between desired fold line and SMA mesh orientation) and angled folds of 15°, 30°, and 45° are analyzed. The 45° angled fold is considered in terms of two sub-cases: one in which the intersections of the wires are centered inside the power application zone (Intersection heating, Fig. 6d) and another in which

Fig. 6. Location of the heating zone for all the cases considered: (a) Aligned fold, (b) 15° angled fold, (c) 30° angled fold, (d) 45° angled fold with heating zone centered at wire intersections, e) 45° angled fold with heating zone centered between wire intersections, and (f) Film-design fold.

the power application zone is centered at the middle of the wire intersections (midspan heating, Fig. 6e). A single case for the film-design is considered (Fig. 6f).

A schematic of the model dimensions and boundary conditions is presented in Fig. 7. A square sheet with 50 mm sides is utilized in this study. Displacement constraints are applied to the sheet to prevent free body motion. The rectangular zone containing the heated wires has a width of $10t_w$ and is centered

along one centerline of the sheet. The initial temperature for all the simulations is 280 K. All the models have equal volume-specific heat source (\hat{P}_T) for the SMA regions located inside the heating zone. The total applied power P_T for each case is calculated using Eq. 3. The values of P_T for the considered cases are presented in Table 4. Note that the total power required for the film-design fold is an order of magnitude higher than the power required for the mesh-design folds.

Fig. 7. Dimensions and boundary conditions for the finite element model (45° angled fold example).

Table 4. Total applied power for all cases.

Model	P_T [W]
Aligned fold	0.8416
15° Angled fold	1.5634
30° Angled fold	1.5546
45° Angled fold (intersection heating)	1.7048
45° Angled fold (midspan heating)	1.5193
Film-design fold	10.6911

4.3 Finite Element Analysis

The combined thermomechanical response of the heated laminate is assessed using a sequentially coupled approach, where the results of a purely thermal problem considering heat transfer are mapped onto a purely mechanical model providing folding deformation results. This clearly accounts for the influence of temperature on deformation but

not the inverse. Unfortunately, due to the strong thermomechanical coupling inherent in SMAs, this is not an optimal approach to the current analysis problem. However, the mechanical and heat transfer processes are separated in this study due to the unavailability of coupled heat transfer–dynamic/implicit processes in Abaqus [17].

The first analysis corresponds to a heat transfer simulation with no deformations involved. In this analysis, power is applied as a body heat source in the regions shown in Fig. 6 using the thermal load profile shown in Fig. 4. The temperature field on the entire model is recorded at various points in time during the 5 seconds of the heating process. The temperature field is tracked by recording the local temperatures at the nodes of each element in the models. In this analysis, the elastomer sheet is modeled using DC3D20 elements (20-node quadratic heat transfer brick [17]), and the SMA regions are modeled using DS8 elements (8-node heat transfer quadrilateral shell). Regarding the mesh-based design cases, since the wires are modeled using shell elements, they are assumed to have squared cross-sections. Furthermore, the SMA meshes assumed to be continuous at the wire intersections (i.e., three dimensional effects of wire weaving at the intersections of the wires are neglected). These two assumptions (square wires, planar intersections) are compatible with a manufacturing option in which the SMA meshes are laser-cut from a thin film.

The second analysis is a dynamic implicit simulation of the fold operation. The temperature field obtained from the heat transfer analysis is inputted in this simulation as a predefined temperature field. In this analysis, the elastomer sheet is modeled using C3D20R elements (20-node quadratic brick, reduced integration), and the SMA regions are modeled using S8R elements (8-node doubly curved thick shell, reduced integration). The usage of thick shell elements to model the SMA regions reduces the run time of the simulations compared to the usage of three-dimensional elements while capturing the essential bending and uniaxial responses accurately.

5 Results and Discussion

The evolution of θ with respect to time for the studied cases is presented in Fig. 8. The simulations for the 15° angled fold, the 30° angled fold, and the 45° angled fold with intersection heating stopped

before reaching the defined full heating time of 5 seconds. This is due to lack of convergence in the iterative solver caused by local structural instabilities, especially at the sheet edges. In the future, an *explicit* implementation of the SMA model will be utilized along with an explicit global solver to avoid this. Such an approach will eliminate convergence issues completely, thought at the expense of local solution accuracy at the wrinkled regions.

Configurations of the folding sheets for all the considered cases are presented in Figs. 9–14, where temperature and martensitic volume fraction contours are clearly shown. The deformation scale factor is set to 2 to better highlight the folding behavior. None of the mesh-based design cases showed folding angle reversal before the heating step ended or the solution failed to converge. This provides evidence that the staggered mesh configuration prevent the problem of heat conduction from one layer of SMA wires to the other, which would result in undesired actuation of the unheated mesh of SMA wires. Unfortunately, this is not the case for the film-based design, which shows a folding reversal approximately after 4 seconds of heating time.

Fig. 8. Evolution of θ with time for the considered cases.

Fig. 9. Configurations of the aligned fold case during the folding maneuver. Final configuration corresponds to the end of the analysis ($t = 5$ out of 5 seconds total). The contour plots show temperature and martensite volume fraction.

It should be noted that the folding angle at the end of the heating step or at the time when the solution failed to converge is lower for all the mesh-based design cases than for the film-based case. This shows that the mesh-based design is able to provide higher quality folds than the film-based design for the same amount of volume-specific applied power. Furthermore, the power required for the mesh-based design cases is approximately an order of magnitude

Fig. 10. Configurations of the 15° angled fold case during the folding maneuver. Final configuration corresponds to the end of the analysis ($t = 2$ out of 5 seconds total). The contour plots show temperature and martensite volume fraction.

lower than the power required for the film-design case as shown in Table 4.

The two cases for 45° angled folds have a better folding performance than the aligned fold. Nevertheless, their folding maneuver requires about the double of the power required by the aligned fold (see Table 4).

Difference in the performance of the two 45° angled fold cases indicates that for the mesh-based design,

Fig. 11. Configurations of the 30° angled fold case during the folding maneuver. Final configuration corresponds to the end of the analysis ($t = 1.8$ out of 5 seconds total). The contour plots show temperature and martensite volume fraction.

folding performance not only depends on orientation of the heating zone but also on its location.

The obtained folds, while not having a folding angle near 0°, allow for the creation of lower θ forms by the implementation of multiple folds [14].

Fig. 12. Configurations of the 45° angled fold case during the folding maneuver. The heating area in this case is centered at the wire intersections. Final configuration corresponds to the end of the analysis (t = 4.4 out of 5 seconds total). The contour plots show temperature and martensite volume fraction.

Fig. 13. Configurations of the 45° angled fold case during the folding maneuver. The heating area in this case is centered between wire intersections. Final configuration corresponds to the end of the analysis (t = 5 out of 5 seconds total). The contour plots show temperature and martensite volume fraction.

6 Conclusions

In this study, the performance of two designs for SMA-based self-folding laminate sheets was compared via finite element simulations. The laminate consisted of two layers of thermally-actuated SMA separated by a compliant elastomer layer. In the film-based design, the outer layers are

homogeneously pre-strained SMA films. The mesh-based design considers the outer layers to be composed of two orthogonal sets of parallel pre-strained SMA wires. Additional features for the mesh-based design are the location and orientation of the two SMA layers relative to each other. In this work only the staggered mesh-based design was

Fig. 14. Configurations of the film design fold case during the folding maneuver. Final configuration corresponds to the end of the analysis ($t = 5$ out of 5 seconds total). The contour plots show temperature and martensite volume fraction.

considered, where the meshes of SMA wires are co-oriented but offset by one half their periodicity in both planar directions. The choice of such design was made based on results from a previous work [14]. Table 5 presents a comparison of different aspects between the two designs.

Table 5. Comparison between the studied laminate designs.

Aspect	Film design	Mesh design
Pre-straining	More difficult. Requires homogeneous and two-dimensional pre-strain of the SMA films	Less difficult. Pre-strain of the wires is unidirectional. If meshes are laser-cut from a film, pre-straining may become difficult
Installation	Less difficult. Requires bonding of three laminae	More difficult. Requires the construction of uniform meshes of SMA wires. This problem could be eliminated if meshes are laser-cut from a film
Power requirements	High	Low
Recoverable transformation strain	$H/2$ at any given direction	H in the directions of the wires alignment
Local folding performance	Isotropic and homogeneous	Polar symmetry of 90° . Depends also in the location of the heating zone
Heat transfer issues	Largely affect the folding performance	Reduced by the adoption of the staggered mesh design
Laminate density	High	Low

The finite element simulations showed that the folding angle at the end of the heating step or at the time when the solution failed to converge was lower for all the mesh-based design cases than for the film-based case. This indicated that the mesh-based design is able to provide higher quality folds than the film-based design for the same amount of volume-specific applied power.

In the future, an explicit implementation of the SMA model will be utilized in a globally explicit and fully thermally coupled framework to analyze this mechanics problem. This approach will eliminate convergence issues at the expense of accuracy in wrinkled regions of the laminate. In addition, future

work includes modeling of the thermomechanical behavior of the SMA meshes using effective lamina properties. Homogenization of the SMA meshes into an effective lamina will be performed for the purposes of computational efficiency and to exploit the tools of laminate plate theory for the modeling of this active composite.

Based on the results from this work, we believe that it can eventually be possible to use this self-folding laminate sheet to develop reprogrammable self-folding complex structures.

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